

These results indicate that supplementary pollination during the pollen grain spreading peak of the male parent had more effect on seed yield than the previous method of pollinating each half hour from maternal flowering to end of flowering of male parent. Seed set increased more than 7.6% and seed yield 8%.

We devised a new technique for supplementary pollination. A nylon rope 0.4 cm in diameter is pulled at 1 m/s along the length of the plots, to scatter pollen grains during the spreading peak. This is carried out two times for each peak, at a 15-min interval, in double peaks; 3-4 times for only one peak. ■

Flowering curves of CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines. Lingling, Hunan, China, 1987-89.

F₁ fertility in indica/japonica crosses

Zhang Xian-guang, Food Crops Institute, Hubei Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Wuhan 430064, China

Low F₁ fertility in crosses of indica and japonica is still a problem. In 1988, we tested the F₁ fertility of two sets of combinations under irrigated conditions. One set was a direct japonica/indica cross (a native japonica variety was crossed with an exotic indica); the other was a modified japonica/indica cross (an advanced line or native japonica variety de-

rived from indica/japonica was crossed with a japonica or an indica parent).

Modified japonicalindica crosses showed significantly higher spikelet fertility (74.1-90.25%) than the typical japonica/indica cross (9.75-35.75%) (see table).

The sterility of F₁ hybrids in direct indica/japonica cross was reportedly the result of genic or cryptic structural hybridity between chromosomes of the

indica and japonica varieties. We infer that the higher fertility in the modified japonicalindica crosses must be the result of the effectiveness of the advanced lines or native japonica varieties used as bridge parents. They presumably carry either dominant genes, to neutralize the effects of recessive complementary lethal genes in the indica and/or japonica variety, or wide compatible genes, to overcome the hybrid sterility barrier. ■

Comparison of F₁ fertility in japonica/indica crosses. Wuhan, China, 1988.

Cross	Fertility (%)
<i>Direct japonica/indica</i>	
LK58/IR36	9.75
HLR4/IR36	16.46
Gh 4/IR28	35.35
105/TKM6	19.82
H857/TKM6	24.23
Mean (x ₂)	21.22
LSD	9.59
<i>Modified japonica/indica</i>	
607 ^a /Longfu 6 ^b	86.53
607/Bamboo rice ^c	90.25
6107 ^a /VN51 ^c	77.70
6107/857 ^b	87.00
HLRS ^b /GS1 ^c	86.37
HLR5/I 636 ^c	74.10
Mean (x ₁)	83.66
LSD	6.28
t = 13.01 > 1% level	

^a Advanced line. ^b Japonica variety derived from an indica/japonica cross. ^c Indica variety.

Use of male gametocide to induce complete male sterility in a partially male sterile rice

Huang Qun-ce and Wang Li-zhu, Biological Department, Xiangtan Teacher's College, P.O. Box 411201, Xiangtan, Hunan, China

Photoperiod-sensitive genic male-sterile rice (PGMSR) is also very sensitive to temperature. While photoperiod is relatively even from year to year, temperature is variable. This means a PGMSR grown in the summer can show variation in pollen sterility, making it unsuitable as female parent in hybrid seed production.

We evaluated a new indica PGMSR, CIS28-15, that was isolated from a B₉F₄ progeny of the cross Caloro/IR28. The critical stage of its sterility-transformation is about 20 Jul, with fertility-transformation 5 Sep under normal conditions in Xiangtan (29° N). But in 1989, male

sterility in the field was not complete between 20 Jul and 15 Aug because the air temperature was unusually low (mean 23 °C) and fluctuated widely.

We sought to induce complete pollen sterility by spraying the male gametocide (CH₃As O₃Zn.H₂O) in 30, 40, 50, and 60 ppm concentrations on the leaves of CIS28-15 at 5 d before heading. Other plants of CIS28-15 were sprayed with plain water. The experiment had four replications, with 20 hills of 1 plant each.

Initiation of panicle primordium starts about 30 d before heading. From 20 Jul to 15 Aug, we recorded the heading date of every panicle, including those of the main shoot and all tillers, to infer the development stage of each panicle when the plant was sprayed with the male gametocide. Observations on pollen and spikelet fertility were made on bagged panicles and open-pollinated panicles.

The results indicated the following (see table):